

D4.4 Satisfaction survey and recommendations for mentoring

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Author(s)	Xavier Eekhout Chicharro
Other Contributors	
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Information in this report that may influence other GEARING-Roles tasks

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T4.3	Mentoring programme pilot for R2 female

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GEARING-Roles project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that will bring together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project therefore has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training in this space, mentoring activities, awareness raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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List of Abbreviations

- D Deliverable
- UDEUSTO Universidad de Deusto
- IGOT-UL Geographic Institute and Spatial Planning - University of Lisbon
- UL University of Ljubljana
- SU Sabanci University
- OBU Oxford Brookes University
- ETAg Estonian Research Council
- FECYT Fundación Española de Ciencia Y Tecnología (EURAXESS Spain Coordinators)
- GEP Gender Equality Plan

Executive Summary

This report compiles the information collected through the exit survey of FELISE, which was prepared to evaluate the satisfaction of the researchers, both mentees and mentors, participating in the FELISE mentoring programme. The report presents results on the level of engagement of the participants and their evaluation of the different parts of the programme, as well as recommendations for future mentoring programmes inspired by FELISE.

1. FELISE mentoring programme

FELISE mentoring programme was a common gender intervention applied in all of the gender equality plans (GEPs) implementing partners of GEARING Roles:

- University of Deusto (ES), UDEUSTO
- Geographic Institute and Spatial Planning - University of Lisbon (PT), IGOT-UL
- Faculty of Arts of the University of Ljubljana (SI), UL
- Sabanci University (TR), SU
- Oxford Brookes University (UK), OBU
- Estonian Research Council (EE), ETAg

The programme was coordinated by Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología (FECYT), although all partners contributed to its design and implementation, particularly in the engagement of participants.

The implementation process of FELISE was:

1. Design of the programme: November 2019 – March 2020
2. Preparing programme resources:
3. Dissemination and recruitment of participants: May 2020 – June 2020
4. Registration of participants and matching: June 2020
5. Mentoring period: July 2020 – February 2021
6. Satisfaction survey to mentors and mentees: March 2021 – May 2021

This report presents the outcomes of the final evaluation. A full description of the programme can be found in *D4.3 Report on the results of the mentoring programme scheme*.

2. Satisfaction Survey

Upon the finalization of the mentoring period (28th February 2021) an online survey for mentees and mentors was prepared by FECYT with the contribution of UDEUSTO. The survey was distributed on the 14th of April 2021 and remained open until the 6th of May 2021. Several reminders to the programme participants were sent within this period. Next, the content of both surveys is detailed:

Mentee satisfaction survey

(*) Mandatory questions

SATISFACTION WITH THE PROGRAMME

1. Please rate your general level of satisfaction with the programme *
 1. Not satisfied
 2. Slightly satisfied
 3. Moderately satisfied
 4. Very satisfied
 5. Extremely satisfied
2. Please rate your level of satisfaction with your mentor *
 1. Not satisfied

2. Slightly satisfied
 3. Moderately satisfied
 4. Very satisfied
 5. Extremely satisfied
3. How many meetings did you finally have with your mentor? *
 - a. One
 - b. Two
 - c. Three
 - d. Four
 - e. Five
 - f. More than five
 4. Please rate your level of satisfaction with your sponsor (if applicable)
 - a. Not satisfied
 - b. Slightly satisfied
 - c. Moderately satisfied
 - d. Very satisfied
 - e. Extremely satisfied
 5. How many meetings did you finally have with your sponsor?
 - a. One
 - b. Two
 - c. More than two
 6. Did you tackle the topics you were most interested in with your mentor?
 - a. Yes
 - b. Partially
 - c. NoPlease clarify, if necessary
 7. Did you tackle the topics you were most interested in with your sponsor (if applicable)?
 - a. Yes
 - b. Partially
 - c. NoPlease clarify, if necessary
 8. Do you believe that a different mentor match (i.e. a mentor with a different profile) would have allowed you to better meet your individual aims? *
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. PartiallyPlease clarify, if necessary
 9. Do you believe that a different sponsor match (i.e. a sponsor with a different profile) would have allowed you to better meet your individual aims?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. PartiallyPlease clarify, if necessary
 10. Do you expect to have further contacts with your mentor? *
 - a. Yes

b. No

11. Do you expect to have further contacts with your sponsor (is applicable)?

- a. Yes
- b. No

12. Please rate the FELISE Mentoring Handbook provided *

- 1. Not useful
- 2. Somehow useful
- 3. Useful
- 4. Very useful

13. Please rate the FELISE Personal Career Plan template provided *

- 1. Not useful
- 2. Somehow useful
- 3. Useful
- 4. Very useful

14. Please rate the on-line training “Professional development planning for researchers” (28 October 2020) *

- 1. Not useful
- 2. Somehow useful
- 3. Useful
- 4. Very useful

15. Please rate the on-line training “Progressing in academia” (18 November 2020)*

- 1. Not useful
- 2. Somehow useful
- 3. Useful
- 4. Very useful

16. Please rate the support received by the FELISE coordination team *

- 1. Very low
- 2. Low
- 3. Medium
- 4. High
- 5. Very high

LOOKING INTO THE FUTURE OF FELISE

17. Would you recommend this experience to other researchers?

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Partially

Please clarify, if necessary

18. Was the 8 months-duration of the programme appropriate to discuss gender equality issues in academic careers?

- a. Yes
- b. No

If no, explain how it would have worked better for you

19. According to you, should institutions include programmes like FELISE focused on reflecting about gender equality in academic careers and on supporting agents of change?
 - c. Yes
 - d. No
20. Please use this space to share with us what you have learned in the programme, highlights, weaknesses or any other comment, suggestion or claims you think that could help improving future editions.

PERSONAL SITUATION AFTER PARTICIPATING IN FELISE

21. How would you rate your commitment towards gender equality in research and teaching?* (1 being very low and 5 being very high)
22. How would you rate your institution commitment towards gender equality in research and teaching? *(1 being very low and 5 being very high)
23. How would you rate your country of residence's commitment towards gender equality?* (1 being very low and 5 being very high)
24. How much do you know about the policies towards gender equality put in place by your institution? *(1 being very little and 5 being very much)
25. How would you rate the level of gender equality in research in your institution?* (1 being very low and 5 being very high)
26. How would you rate the impact of gender equality measures in:
 - a. your own career* (1 being very negative impact and 5 being very positive impact)
 - b. your institution *(1 being very negative impact and 5 being very positive impact)
27. How would you rate your willingness to be an "agent of change" towards gender equality in your institution (by participating in working groups, moving to management positions, becoming a gender equality Ambassador at your institution, participating in mentoring programs, etc)* (1 being very low willingness and 5 being very high willingness)
28. How much would you say your career is being affected by gender inequality in research?* (1 being very little and 5 being very much)
29. Which are, in your opinion, the main barriers and resistances for gender balance in academic life?*
Free text (1500 characters)
30. In your opinion, how feasible would be overcoming the current barriers and resistances?* Free text (1500 characters)
31. How prepared would you say you are to identify, face and report gender inequalities in research and teaching?* (1 being very little and 5 being very much)

32. How aware would you say you are about your professional skills and your strengths and weaknesses for a job in academia? *(1 being very little aware and 5 being very much aware)
33. How much have you prepared your career progression? *(1 being very little prepared and 5 being very prepared)
34. How good would you say your professional network is? *(1 being very bad and 5 being very good)

Mentor satisfaction survey

(*) Mandatory questions

SATISFACTION WITH THE PROGRAMME

1. Please rate your general level of satisfaction with the programme *
 1. Not satisfied
 2. Slightly satisfied
 3. Moderately satisfied
 4. Very satisfied
 5. Extremely satisfied
2. Please rate your level of satisfaction with your mentee from your institution (mentoring meetings) *
 1. Not satisfied
 2. Slightly satisfied
 3. Moderately satisfied
 4. Very satisfied
 5. Extremely satisfied
3. How many mentoring meetings did you finally have with your mentee from your institution? *
 - a. One
 - b. Two
 - c. Three
 - d. Four
 - e. Five
 - f. More than five
4. Please rate your level of satisfaction with your mentee from another institution, if applicable (sponsoring meetings)
 - a. Not satisfied
 - b. Slightly satisfied
 - c. Moderately satisfied
 - d. Very satisfied
 - e. Extremely satisfied
5. How many meetings did you finally have with your mentee from another institution, if applicable (sponsoring meetings)
 - a. One
 - b. Two
 - c. More than two
6. Do you believe that a different mentoring match (e.g., a mentee with a different research background or in a different career stage) could have benefited more from your support? *
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. Partially

Please clarify, if necessary

7. Do you believe that a different sponsoring match (e.g., a mentee with a different research background or in a different career stage) could have benefited more from your support (if applicable)?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. Partially

Please clarify, if necessary

8. Do you expect to have further contacts with your mentee? *
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

9. Do you expect to have further contacts with your sponsor (is applicable)?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

10. Please rate the FELISE Mentoring Handbook provided *

1. Not useful
2. Somehow useful
3. Useful
4. Very useful

11. Please rate the FELISE Personal Career Plan template provided *

1. Not useful
2. Somehow useful
3. Useful
4. Very useful

12. Please rate how useful the rest of the resources offered by the FELISE programme were for your role as a mentor (i.e., training for mentees and keynote presentations)*

1. Not useful
2. Somehow useful
3. Useful
4. Very useful

13. Please rate the support received by the FELISE coordination team *

1. Very low
2. Low
3. Medium
4. High
5. Very high

LOOKING INTO THE FUTURE OF FELISE

15. Would you recommend this experience to other researchers? *

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Partially

Please clarify, if necessary

16. Was the 8 months-duration of the programme appropriate to discuss gender equality issues in academic careers ?
- Yes
 - No
- If no, explain how it would have worked better for you
17. According to you, should institutions include programmes like FELISE focused on reflecting about gender equality in academic careers and on supporting agents of change? *
- Yes
 - No
- Please clarify, if necessary
18. Please use this space to share with us what you have learned in the programme, highlights, weaknesses or any other comment, suggestion or claims you think that could help improving future editions.

PERSONAL SITUATION AFTER PARTICIPATING IN FELISE

19. How would you rate your commitment towards gender equality in research and teaching? *(1 being very low and 5 being very high)
20. How would you rate your institution commitment towards gender equality in research and teaching?*(1 being very low and 5 being very high)
21. How would you rate your country of residence’s commitment towards gender equality ?*(1 being very low and 5 being very high)
22. How much do you know about the policies towards gender equality put in place by your institution?*(1 being very little and 5 being very much)
23. How would you rate the level of gender equality in research in your institution?*(1 being very low and 5 being very high)
24. How would you rate the impact of gender equality measures in:
- your own career *(1 being very negative impact and 5 being very positive impact)
 - your institution* (1 being very negative positive impact and 5 being very positive impact)
25. How would you rate your willingness to be an “agent of change” towards gender equality in your institution (by participating in working groups, moving to management positions, becoming a gender equality Ambassador at your institution, participating in mentoring programs, etc.) ?*(1 being very little willingness and 5 being very much willingness)
26. How much would you say your career is being affected by gender inequality in research ?*(1 being very little and 5 being very much)
27. How prepared would you say you are to identify, face and report gender inequalities in research and teaching?*(1 being very little and 5 being very much)

3. Level of engagement

Mentees

From the 35 mentees initially engaged, **27 replied to the survey**. The survey remained open for more than 20 days, and several reminders were sent during this period, but the number of replies from IGOT-UL and UL were relatively low. Nevertheless, the fact that a majority of the mentors from those institutions (see Table 4) did provide a reply, suggest that this was due to circumstances beyond the FELISE programme.

MENTEES per GEP implementer		
GEP Implementing institution	Number of replies	%
University of Deusto (ES)	9	100%
Oxford Brookes University	5	83%
IGOT-University of Lisbon (PT)	2	40%
Estonian Research Council (EE)*	4	80%
Sabancı University (TR)	5	83%
University of Ljubljana (SI)**	2	67%

27

*Researchers enrolled by the Estonian Research Council (a research funding organization) actually work in other Estonian research performing organizations

** Early in the mentoring phase, a mentor from the University of Ljubljana had to step down from the programme. Her mentee declined being matched with another mentor although she remained informed and invited to other FELISE activities along the duration of the programme (e.g., trainings and keynote presentations).

Table 1. Replies from the mentees to the satisfaction survey

The average number of mentoring meetings reported by mentees was more than 3, with 60% of the respondents having participated in 5 or more of the requested meetings with their mentor.

Number of mentoring meetings	Mentees	%
One	5	18,52%
Two	1	3,70%
Three	1	3,70%
Four	3	11,11%
Five	12	44,44%
More than five	5	18,52%

27 100,00%

Table 2. Number of meetings with mentor reported by the mentees

In the case of the sponsoring meetings with a mentor from another institution, only 15 of the respondents confirmed having met with their sponsor. Approximately half of them had at least met two times as requested by the programme.

Number of sponsoring meetings	Mentees	%
One	7	46,67%
Two	5	33,33%
More than two	3	20,00%
	15	100,00%

Table 3. Number of meetings with sponsors reported by mentees

Mentors

From the 35 mentors initially engaged, 23 replied to the survey. Their distribution per GEP implementing institution was:

MENTORS per GEP implementer		
GEP Implementing institution	Number of replies	%
University of Deusto (ES)	7	78%
Oxford Brookes University	4	67%
IGOT-University of Lisbon (PT)	4	80%
Estonian Research Council (EE)*	3	60%
Sabancı University (TR)	2	33%
University of Ljubljana (SI)**	3	100%
	23	

Table 4. Replies from the mentors/sponsors to the satisfaction survey

Like in the case of the mentees, the mentors responding to the survey reported participating on average in more than 3 mentoring meetings with their mentee, and 60% completed at least the 5 meetings requested by the programme.

Number of mentoring meetings	Mentors	%
One	2	8,70%
Two	1	4,35%
Three	4	17,39%
Four	2	8,70%
Five	9	39,13%
More than five	5	21,74%
	23	100,00%

Table 5. Number of meetings with mentee from within the institution, in the role of mentor

Out of the 23 respondents, 11 confirmed having participated in **sponsoring meeting** with mentees from other institutions and 6 of them completed at least the 2 meetings requested by the programme.

Number of sponsoring meetings	Mentors	%
One	5	45,45%
Two	5	45,45%
More than two	1	9,09%
	11	100,00%

Table 6. Number of meetings with mentee from outside the institution, in the role of sponsor

4. Level of satisfaction

Mentees

In terms of overall satisfaction with the programme, almost 60% of the mentees that replied were either Very Satisfied or Extremely satisfied, going to 90% including those Moderately satisfied.

In a similar way, the level of satisfaction with the assigned mentors was also high with a similar percentage in all levels, suggesting that in general terms those mentees less satisfied with the programme were due to not having found an appropriate match.

This can be confirmed by the fact that slightly more than 10% of the mentees were not able to address the topics in which they were more interested.

Based on qualitative replies offered, this impossibility to address the topics of interest could have also been caused by changes in the work plan due to professional commitments (e.g., having to devote more time than expected to a research application), and not necessarily to not being a proper match.

Actually, when questioned about the possible impact of a different match, less than 20% considered that this would have helped them to better achieve their individual goals.

This situation is mirrored by the fact that almost 80% of the mentees replying they have plans to keep in touch with their mentor.

In regards to the sponsoring meetings, the situation appears to be slightly different with the level of satisfaction with the assigned sponsor being relatively heterogeneous among the 14 replies received.

Nevertheless, more than 90% of the mentees who met with their sponsor were able to discuss topics of their interest.

This is considered a relatively good result especially taking into account that several qualitative comments explained that, even within the same research domain (the criteria used to match mentees and sponsors, see D4.3) the fields of research were still too different for a proper sponsoring relationship.

Finally, regarding the resources offered by the mentoring programme, the mentees provided the following ratings:

Figure 10. Mentee rating of the On-line training “Professional development planning for researchers” (28 October 2020)

Figure 11. Mentee rating On-line training “Progressing in academia” (18 November 2020)

Figure 12. Mentee rating of the support received by the FELISE coordination team

Mentors

In terms of overall satisfaction with the programme, the rating was slightly lower than among mentees with more than 65% replying being either Very Satisfied or Extremely satisfied. Nevertheless, in comparison to the mentees, none of the respondents were unsatisfied with their participation.

Figure 13. Overall satisfaction with the programme - mentors/sponsors

In regards to the level of satisfaction with the assigned mentee, more than 90% recognised being Very Satisfied or Extremely satisfied with the match.

Figure 14. Level of satisfaction with the mentee assigned to act as mentors

Although this did not prevent from a majority of the respondents (82,61%) thinking that with a different match, they would have been able to provide a more complete support to the mentee.

Figure 15. Could a different mentee match improve the level of support provided as mentor?

Most of the qualitative comments received in this sense considered that similar research backgrounds would have allowed for a better support also in the mentoring relationships.

Nevertheless it is very positive to learn that despite this possible area of improvement, more than 95% of the mentors replying had the intention of keeping in touch with their mentee beyond the duration of the programme.

Figure 16. Do you expect to have further contacts with your mentee?

In the case of the sponsoring relationships, more than 60% of the mentors who confirmed having sponsoring meetings were either Very Satisfied or Extremely Satisfied with the mentee from another institution with which they were matched.

Nevertheless, the amount of support that they could offer was limited, with a majority of the mentors considering that a different sponsoring match would have partially or totally (Yes) allowed them to be more efficient sponsors.

In regards to the FELISE resources offered, the ratings of the mentors were as follows:

Figure 21. Mentor/sponsor rating of the support received by the FELISE coordination team

5. Recommendations for the future

Several questions to both, mentees and mentors were aimed at compiling recommendations for future mentoring programmes based on their experience with FELISE.

Recommending the FELISE approach

In regards to recommending peers to participate in a similar programme, a majority clearly supported the idea. Based on the comments received, those not convinced by the approach applied in programme mostly linked their reply to not having been able to take advantage of the sponsoring relationship due to discrepancies in their research fields.

Mentees

Mentors

Suitability of similar initiatives

Regardless of the possible improvements to the FELISE model, most participants were clearly convinced about the fact that research institutions should include programmes like FELISE focused on reflecting about gender equality in academic career, as a key support to agents of change, and thus structural change.

Mentees

Mentors

Duration of the programme

When questioned about the extension of FELISE there was also a clear majority agreeing that the 8 months established had been appropriate, although a few mentees would favour longer durations (i.e., one year at least).

Mentees

Mentors

Additional activities/content

Qualitative input from both the mentees and the mentors allowed us to compile recommendation for possible elements which could have contributed to improving FELISE:

- Having the participation in the mentoring programme count as working hours
- Foster meetings between mentees, at least those within the own institution
- Less focus on individual changes and more focus towards changing the academic careers
- Opportunities to meet physically
- Allowing mentees to propose mentors
- More group discussion sessions
- More people (more pairs) engaged in the programme
- Including topics related to wider career options (external funding, spinouts, etc.)

Many of them refer to the limited capacity to favour on-site networking of the participants. These, unfortunately could not be implemented as part of FELISE due to the mobility restrictions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. As a matter of fact, a group mentoring session was originally planned as part of the 2nd GEARING Roles Annual Conference (November 2020), but had to be cancelled once the on-site conference was discarded.

In any case, it is quite clear that a mentoring programme such as FELISE, which is virtual to a large degree, benefits very much from occasional face to face activities.